

Examination of Communication and Domestic Violence against Women in Port Harcourt City Local Government Area, Rivers State Nigeria.

Chidinma N. Ejekwu, PhD

Department of Mass Communication

Faculty of Information and Communication Technology.

Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic, Rumuola Port Harcourt Nigeria.

chidinmaejekwu85@gmail.com

08164725044

&

Sunny-Gobo Oribime Fortune

Department of Mass Communication, Faculty of Information and Communication Technology.

Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic, Rumuola Port Harcourt Nigeria.

Oribimegobo2@gmail.com

08135728570

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18181469>

Abstract

This study examined Communication and Domestic Violence against Women in Port Harcourt City Local Government Area Rivers State Nigeria. The study was guided by three objectives, research questions, and hypotheses, and anchored on the Communication Pattern Theory and Social Learning Theory. A Descriptive Survey Design was adopted. The study population comprised 2,245 women drawn from Community-Based Women Organizations (CBWOs) in Port Harcourt Metropolis. A sample of 242 women was selected using the Krejcie and Morgan formula and the Simple Random Sampling Technique. Data were collected using a self-structured questionnaire designed to assess communication patterns, emotional support, and exposure to domestic violence. The research questions were analyzed using mean and standard deviation. Findings revealed that effective communication significantly reduces anxiety, depression, and domestic violence, while fostering mutual understanding, emotional support, and cohesion among family members. Empirical studies in related contexts have shown that open and healthy communication patterns within families are associated with lower levels of intimate partner violence, as they promote emotional stability, conflict resolution, and trust among couples.

Evidence also indicates that families who practice active listening, empathy, and non-verbal sensitivity experience fewer cases of physical and Psychological abuse, as communication acts as a preventive and corrective mechanism against tension and misunderstanding. These findings suggest that effective communication enhances emotional resilience and serves as a protective factor against domestic violence. Conversely, poor or dysfunctional communication often results in emotional disconnection, unresolved conflicts, and heightened hostility, which increase the likelihood of domestic violence within the household. Empirical evidence shows that when communication is characterized by withdrawal, dominance, or aggression, it reinforces power imbalances and fosters environments where abuse is more likely to occur. Additionally, studies based on social learning perspectives indicate that communication behaviors—whether positive or negative—are often learned and modeled from parental or societal influences, thereby perpetuating either constructive or violent relational patterns across generations. Based on these findings, the study recommends that the government, in collaboration with CBWOs, should organize capacity-building seminars and workshops for both women and men to promote effective family communication, empathy, and conflict resolution skills. Furthermore, community leaders should model constructive communication to foster marital resilience and relational harmony. Enhancing communication competence within families can thus serve as a sustainable strategy for reducing domestic violence and promoting family wellbeing in Port Harcourt Metropolis and beyond.

Keywords: Family Communication, Prevalence, Domestic Violence, Women, Protective Factor and Resilience.

Introduction

Domestic violence remains a pervasive societal issue that disproportionately affects women and undermines their mental, emotional, and physical well-being regardless of age, class, religion and cultural boundaries. Defined broadly as any form of abusive behavior—physical, emotional, psychological, sexual, or economic, perpetrated or used by one family or household member to gain and maintain control over another, domestic violence has increasingly become a recurring issue that affects the emotional well-being and psychological safety of women.

In Port Harcourt, a significant number of women experience abuse in various forms, including physical, emotional, and psychological violence, often perpetrated by intimate partners. While

research has explored economic dependence, cultural norms, and legal inadequacies as contributors to domestic violence, communication within the family setting has received comparatively less attention (Umennuihe et al., 2023). Domestic violence refers to abusive behaviors used by one partner to gain or maintain control over another intimate partner. It includes physical, sexual, emotional, economic, or psychological actions or threats (WHO, 2021).

In Nigeria, domestic violence is often underreported due to societal stigma, victim-blaming, and inadequate enforcement of protective laws. Communication is central to the expression of needs, resolution of conflicts, and building of intimacy; when dysfunctional, it can foster misunderstanding, conflict, and even abuse (Knapp & Daly, 2011). Effective communication is a cornerstone of healthy relationships.

In recent years, considerable attention has been drawn to the role of communication as both a protective and risk factor for domestic violence. Communication within the family is not merely about exchanging information; it is deeply rooted in relational patterns, cultural expectations, power dynamics, and emotional expression. These patterns significantly influence how family members negotiate conflicts, express needs, or exert control. According to Galvin, Braithwaite, and Bylund (2018), family communication serves as the foundation for relational development and can either strengthen emotional bonds or intensify tension and discord.

Family communication refers to the verbal and non-verbal interactions that occur among family members. It is through communication that families' express emotions, resolve conflicts, establish rules, and share expectations. The nature, quality and patterns of these interactions play a significant role in shaping behaviors, managing stress and navigating disagreements. When communication within the family is open, respectful and supportive, it can foster understanding,

emotional security and conflict resolution. Conversely, poor communication marked by hostility, silence, manipulation or misunderstanding- can escalate tensions and contribute to violent behavior.

In patriarchal societies such as Nigeria, where traditional gender roles often place men in dominant positions and women in submissive roles, family communication patterns can reflect hierarchical structures that either perpetuate or challenge violence. Poor communication -characterized by hostility, silence, lack of empathy, or avoidance - has been identified as a contributor to escalating tension and, eventually, physical or emotional abuse (Koerner & Fitzpatrick, 2002). Conversely, families that encourage open dialogue, emotional expression, and mutual respect are more likely to foster a culture of understanding and conflict resolution without resorting to violence.

The implications of dysfunctional family communication are profound. Women who experience poor spousal communication may feel isolated, invalidated, or powerless, which increases their vulnerability to abuse and reduces their ability to seek help. On the other hand, effective communication within the family has been associated with improved mental health outcomes, including reduced anxiety, depression, and stress, and enhanced emotional resilience (Galvin et al., 2018). In this context, family communication does not only serve a functional role but operates as a psychosocial protective factor against the occurrence and recurrence of domestic violence.

Despite increasing global discourse on domestic violence, there remains a scarcity of empirical data focused on the communicative dynamics within Nigerian families, particularly among women affiliated with grassroots and community-based organizations. In Port Harcourt, community-based organizations have played a vital role in advocating for women's rights and welfare, offering a critical entry point for studying domestic issues within the family structure. Understanding how

communication patterns affect the prevalence of domestic violence among this demographic is essential for designing targeted interventions that address not just the symptoms of abuse but its relational and communicative roots.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the growing awareness, advocacy and efforts to combat domestic violence against women, the phenomenon continues to escalate, particularly among women in urban centers like Port Harcourt metropolis. Numerous interventions - legal, social, and religious - have been introduced to curb this menace; yet domestic violence remains a persistent and deeply rooted issue. While much of the existing literature focuses on socio-economic and cultural causes of domestic violence, less attention has been given to intra-family communication patterns as a potential contributing factor.

Communication plays a crucial role in shaping emotional connection, conflict resolution, and behavioral responses among family members. When communication is characterized by openness, empathy, and mutual respect, it promotes understanding and emotional resilience. However, when it is marked by silence, aggression, misunderstanding, or dominance, it can escalate conflict and foster an environment conducive to abuse. In many homes within Port Harcourt, communication between spouses is often hierarchical, with limited opportunities for dialogue or emotional expression—conditions that may normalize or conceal abusive behaviors.

Furthermore, cultural norms and gender expectations in Nigerian society often discourage women from speaking up or seeking help when abused, thereby compounding the impact of poor family communication. There is a critical gap in empirical research exploring how these communication

patterns within families influence the prevalence and intensity of domestic violence among women.

Hence, the major problem this study seeks to address is the lack of empirical evidence on the role of family communication in either mitigating or exacerbating domestic violence. Specifically, it aims to investigate how different patterns of family communication influence the experiences of anxiety, depression, emotional support, and exposure to violence among women in Port Harcourt Metropolis. Without addressing this relational dynamic, efforts to combat domestic violence may remain incomplete and less effective.

Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to examine the influence of Communication and Domestic Violence among Women in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Specifically, the objectives of the study are to:

1. Examine the extent to which communication enhance **emotional resilience** among Women in Port Harcourt Metropolis
2. Determine ways communication **reduce anxiety and depression** among Women in Port Harcourt Metropolis
3. Find out how family communication enhance **family wellbeing** among Women in Port Harcourt Metropolis

Research Questions

The researcher formulated the following research questions that will guide the study:

1. To what extent does communication enhance **emotional resilience** among Women in Port Harcourt Metropolis?
2. How does communication **reduce anxiety and depression** among Women in Port Harcourt Metropolis?
3. How does communication enhance **family wellbeing** among Women in Port Harcourt Metropolis?

REVIEW OF RALATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Review: The Consequences of Domestic Violence on Women

Domestic violence remains one of the most pervasive and devastating violations of women's human rights globally. It involves physical, sexual, emotional, economic, or psychological abuse perpetrated by an intimate partner or family member (World Health Organization [WHO], 2021). While the incidence of domestic violence varies across regions and cultures, the consequences are universally severe and long-lasting. This conceptual review explores the multifaceted consequences of domestic violence on women, categorized into physical, psychological, social, economic, and intergenerational impacts.

Physical Consequences

Women subjected to domestic violence frequently endure physical injuries ranging from bruises and fractures to internal bleeding and disabilities. Repeated abuse may also result in chronic health issues such as hypertension, gastrointestinal problems, and complications with reproductive health (Black et al., 2011). In many cases, the injuries are not only immediate but can lead to long-term disability or even death. According to WHO (2021), approximately 38% of all murders of women worldwide are committed by intimate partners, underscoring the lethal nature of such violence.

Psychological and Emotional Consequences

One of the most devastating impacts of domestic violence is on women's mental health. Prolonged exposure to abuse often results in conditions such as depression, anxiety, post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), and suicidal ideation (Dillon et al., 2013). Victims frequently experience feelings of shame, guilt, helplessness, and low self-worth. These psychological effects can persist long after the physical abuse has ended. Research by Devries et al. (2013) found a strong correlation between intimate partner violence and mental health disorders, including substance use and suicidal behavior.

Social Consequences

Domestic violence also severely limits women's social lives. Abusers often isolate their victims from family, friends, and community networks as a means of control (Jewkes et al., 2015). This social isolation hinders their ability to seek help or support. Moreover, in many societies, women who speak out about abuse are stigmatized or blamed, further compounding their trauma. Such social ostracization discourages victims from reporting abuse or accessing support services, trapping them in cycles of violence.

Economic Consequences

Economic dependency is both a cause and consequence of domestic violence. Abusive partners often restrict women's access to education, employment, or financial resources, creating a dependency that makes leaving the relationship difficult (Adams et al., 2013). Women may lose jobs due to injuries, absenteeism, or the psychological effects of abuse. Additionally, they may incur significant healthcare costs and face housing insecurity when attempting to escape abusive

environments. Studies have shown that economic abuse, such as controlling access to money or employment, is a prevalent form of coercion in abusive relationships (Postmus et al., 2012).

Intergenerational Consequences

The impact of domestic violence extends beyond the immediate victim to affect children and future generations. Children who witness domestic violence are at higher risk of developing emotional and behavioral problems, academic difficulties, and social dysfunction (Kitzmann et al., 2003). Moreover, exposure to violence during childhood increases the likelihood of perpetuating or experiencing abuse in adulthood, thereby perpetuating a cycle of violence (Widom & Maxfield, 2001). This intergenerational transmission underscores the societal cost of unchecked domestic violence.

Legal and Justice System Implications

Although many countries have enacted laws to protect women from domestic violence, barriers remain in accessing justice. Fear of retaliation, lack of trust in legal institutions, and limited awareness of rights prevent many women from reporting abuse (UN Women, 2020). Inadequate enforcement of protective laws and cultural norms that normalize violence against women further obstruct justice. Legal battles, especially over child custody, can also be manipulated by abusers to continue exerting control over victims.

In the Nigerian context, particularly within Port Harcourt, communication within families is often shaped by cultural expectations that reinforce male dominance and female subordination. This cultural norm may suppress women's voices and prevent the reporting or discussion of abuse, thus perpetuating domestic violence.

The Interplay Between Communication and Domestic Violence

Communication can either de-escalate or trigger conflict. Families that encourage emotional expression and joint problem-solving are less likely to experience prolonged tension or violence. In contrast, poor communication—marked by shouting, silence, withdrawal, or sarcasm—may create an emotionally toxic environment that breeds violence. Moreover, communication styles often reflect power relations within the family, which are central to understanding the dynamics of abuse (Knapp & Daly, 2011).

Theoretical Framework

This study explores the relationship between family communication and the prevalence of domestic violence among women in Port Harcourt Metropolis. To examine this phenomenon, the study is anchored in two complementary theoretical perspectives: Family Communication Patterns Theory and Social Learning Theory. These frameworks provide insight into how communication behaviors within family systems influence conflict resolution, power dynamics, and the transmission of violent behavior

Family Communication Patterns Theory

Family Communication Patterns (FCP) Theory, as developed by McLeod and Chaffee (1972) and further refined by Fitzpatrick and Ritchie (1994), posits that families develop relatively stable patterns of communication that influence how members interact, interpret conflict, and make decisions. FCP Theory is structured around two key dimensions: conversation orientation and conformity orientation.

Conversation orientation reflects the degree to which families encourage open dialogue, expression of opinions, and participation in decision-making.

Conformity orientation pertains to the extent to which family communication emphasizes homogeneity of attitudes, obedience, and hierarchical relationships i.e. the extent to which family members are expected to align with the family's beliefs, norms, and authority figures

Families high in conformity and low in conversation orientation (protective families) tend to discourage open expression and enforce rigid authority structures. Such communication climates may inhibit the reporting of abuse, suppress the emotional wellbeing of women, and reinforce patriarchal control. Conversely, families high in conversation orientation and low in conformity (pluralistic families) promote open discussion and egalitarianism, which can foster mutual respect and conflict resolution (Koerner & Fitzpatrick, 2002).

Social Learning Theory

Social Learning Theory, proposed by Albert Bandura (1977), asserts that human behavior is learned through observation, imitation, and reinforcement. According to this theory, behaviors are not only learned through direct experience but also by watching others—particularly significant others such as parents, partners, or authority figures.

This framework suggests that domestic violence can be a learned behavior, modeled within the family environment and normalized over time. For instance, a child who grows up witnessing violence between parents may come to perceive such behavior as acceptable or expected in adult relationships. Similarly, a man raised in an environment where women were demeaned or abused may internalize such behaviors and reproduce them in his own relationships. (Bandura, 1986).

In the context of domestic violence, Social Learning Theory posits that exposure to violence within the family increases the likelihood of individuals adopting similar behaviors in adulthood, either as perpetrators or victims. Women who witnessed inter-parental violence during childhood or who were raised in homes where violence was a communicative strategy may be more likely to enter or remain in abusive relationships due to normalized expectations of relational dynamics (Straus, Gelles & Steinmetz, 1980).

This theoretical lens is particularly relevant in Port Harcourt, where traditional patriarchal norms and systemic socio-economic pressures can reinforce gendered power imbalances. In many households, violent behaviors may be inadvertently reinforced through cultural silence, societal impunity, or religious doctrines, thereby making them cyclical and intergenerational.

By applying these theories, the study aims to uncover the underlying communicative and behavioral patterns that contribute to the high prevalence of domestic violence among women in Port Harcourt Metropolis, and to inform culturally sensitive interventions that promote non-violent family communication and gender equity.

Empirical Review

Several empirical studies have examined the relationship between communication patterns and domestic violence. Onyinye and Alabi (2020) found that families with open and supportive communication reported significantly lower rates of intimate partner violence. Similarly, Chukwu and Eze (2021) discovered that in Rivers State, authoritarian family structures and poor communication channels were predictors of spousal abuse. In an international context, Holt et al. (2008) emphasized that effective family communication serves as a protective mechanism that promotes emotional safety and mitigates the risk of intimate partner violence.

Ojedokun and Atoi (2018) conducted a study in southwestern Nigeria to assess the relationship between communication styles and spousal violence. Findings revealed that passive-aggressive and avoidant communication patterns among couples significantly increased the likelihood of emotional, verbal, and physical abuse. The study emphasized the need for assertive communication as a preventive strategy for domestic violence.

Nwankwo, Obi, & Nwoke (2017) examined the prevalence of domestic violence among married women in Port Harcourt and found that poor interpersonal communication and lack of conflict resolution skills were major predictors of physical and psychological abuse. The research, which involved 300 women in the metropolis, concluded that families that engaged in open and respectful communication experienced fewer incidents of domestic violence.

Eze and Ibekwe (2020) focused on the role of communication in conflict management within families in Rivers State. Their findings indicated that families with high conversation orientation—those who freely discuss feelings, issues, and concerns—reported significantly lower rates of spousal abuse compared to those with high conformity orientation, where obedience and hierarchy are prioritized over dialogue.

Adegoke and Oladeji (2016) studied 250 married women in Lagos and found that poor communication was not only a precursor to physical violence but also a barrier to reporting it. Women who lacked the ability or space to express their concerns within the family system often suffered prolonged abuse due to silence or cultural expectations.

Ukonu and Eze (2021) explored the effect of communication patterns on women's exposure to domestic violence in the South-South geopolitical zone, including Port Harcourt. Their mixed-method study revealed that communication breakdown and gendered power imbalances are

intricately linked, as many women are socialized to submit and avoid “talking back,” further entrenching cycles of abuse.

Ijeoma and Ezenwa (2019) conducted a qualitative study among victims of domestic violence in Rivers State. They observed that many women experienced emotional neglect and verbal abuse long before physical violence began, and most attributed the escalation to a lack of meaningful communication with their partners

Holt, Buckley, and Whelan (2008) reviewed the impact of domestic violence on children and families, concluding that poor intra-family communication was a major contributor to persistent abuse. They argued that families who lack healthy communication strategies often resort to physical or emotional control to resolve disagreements.

Similarly, a study by Lloyd and Emery (2000) found that couples in the United States who reported high-quality communication also experienced lower levels of conflict and reported greater marital satisfaction. Conversely, communication marked by contempt, withdrawal, and blame was strongly associated with emotional and physical abuse.

In the Nigerian context, Onyinye and Alabi (2020) conducted a study on domestic violence in Lagos and found that women in families with authoritarian communication styles were more likely to report emotional and physical abuse. Chukwu and Eze (2021), in a study conducted in Rivers State, observed that dysfunctional communication—characterized by emotional suppression and lack of dialogue—was a predictor of spousal abuse and marital dissatisfaction.

Another study by Obasi and Igwe (2019) in Enugu State highlighted that lack of mutual communication was a major trigger for domestic violence, particularly in economically strained

households. They also found that when spouses had regular, open conversations, the frequency and intensity of conflict decreased significantly.

Methodology

A Descriptive Survey Research Design was adopted. The study population comprised 2,245 women drawn from Community-Based Women Organizations (CBWOs) in Port Harcourt Metropolis. A sample of 242 women was selected using the Krcjcie and Morgan's formula and the Simple Random Sampling Technique. Data were collected using a self-structured questionnaire. The research questions were analyzed using mean and standard deviation.

Results

Research Question 1: To what extent does family communication enhance **emotional resilience** among Women in Port Harcourt Metropolis?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation analysis on the extent family communication enhance emotional resilience among Women in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

S/ No	Questionnaire Items	Community Based CBWO EXCO			Women Organization CBWO Members		
		Mean \bar{x}	SD	Remarks	Mean \bar{x}	SD	Remarks
1.	Family members feel safe to share fears, sadness, or frustrations without judgment	2.89	0.85	High Extent	2.95	0.86	High Extent
2.	Family communication encourages healthy emotional processing instead of suppression	2.86	0.83	High Extent	2.86	0.84	High Extent
3.	Consistent and honest communication creates an environment of trust	2.78	0.83	High Extent	2.91	0.85	High Extent
4.	Through discussions and joint decision-making, family members model how to handle setbacks and find solutions	2.83	0.84	High Extent	2.82	0.84	High Extent
5.	Family members affirm each other's efforts, achievements, and progress	2.86	0.84	High Extent	2.86	0.84	High Extent
Grand Total		2.84	0.84		2.88	0.85	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The findings presented in Table 1 underscores the significance of family communication in strengthening emotional resilience among women in Port Harcourt Metropolis. With all mean scores above the acceptance mean criterion of 2.5, the findings demonstrates a consistently high extent of agreement among respondents. Specifically, when family members feel safe to share fears of frustrations without judgement (Mean = 2.89 for CBWO Exco and 2.95 for members), emotional openness and mutual support are enhanced. Similarly, communication that encourages healthy emotional processing (Mean = 2.86 for both groups) reduces emotional suppression, while consistent and honest exchanges that foster trust (Mean = 2.78 and 2.91) further build emotional stability. Discussions and joint decision-making that model problem-solving (Mean = 2.83 and 2.82) also contribute to coping skills, while affirming one another’s efforts and achievements (Mean = 2.86 for both groups) reinforces self – worth and confidence. The grand means of 2.84 (CBWO Exco) and 2.88 (members) affirm that family communication plays a significant role in promoting emotional residence and psychological wellbeing among women in the study area.

Research Question 2: How does family communication **reduce anxiety and depression** among Women in Port Harcourt Metropolis?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation analysis on how family communication reduce anxiety and depression among Women in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

S/ No	Questionnaire Items	Community Based CBWO EXCO			Women Organization CBWO Members		
		Mean \bar{x}	SD	Remarks	Mean \bar{x}	SD	Remarks
6.	When family members listen without judgment, express empathy, and validate emotions, it reduces feelings of isolation and self-blame	2.86	0.84	High Extent	2.91	0.85	High Extent

7.	Open discussions help families brainstorm solutions together, model healthy coping mechanisms, and reduce a sense of helplessness	2.83	0.84	High	2.95	0.86	High
				Extent			Extent
8.	Clear communication reduces misinterpretation, tension, and unresolved conflicts all of which are known triggers for anxiety and depression	2.97	0.86	High	2.98	0.86	High
				Extent			Extent
9.	Words of encouragement, praise, and affirmation from family boost self-esteem and confidence	2.94	0.86	High	2.99	0.86	High
				Extent			Extent
10.	When families talk regularly and honestly, they can more easily notice signs of emotional trouble and intervene early	2.97	0.86	High	2.98	0.86	High
				Extent			Extent
Grand Total		2.90	0.85		2.97	0.86	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 2 highlights the significant role of effective family communication in reducing anxiety and depression among women in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The consistently high mean scores across all items, each meeting or surpassing the acceptance mean criterion of 2.5 and above (which was the average mean) indicate a strong consensus among respondents that empathetic listening, open discussions and regular, honest communication contribute substantially to emotional well-being. The results emphasize that supportive and transparent family interactions foster emotional validation, reduce feelings of isolation, and enable early intervention when signs of distress arise. Overall, the table signifies that healthy family communication serves as a vital protective factor against anxiety and depression among women in the community.

Research Question 3: How does family communication enhance **family wellbeing** among Women in Port Harcourt Metropolis

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation analysis on how family communication enhance family wellbeing among Women in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

S/ No	Questionnaire Items	Community Based CBWO EXCO			Women Organization CBWO Members		
		Mean \bar{x}	SD	Remarks	Mean \bar{x}	SD	Remarks
11.	When family members communicate openly and respectfully, they feel safe to express themselves without fear of judgment or rejection	2.83	0.84	High Extent	2.91	0.85	High Extent
12.	Clear communication prevents assumptions and clarifies expectations	2.72	0.82	High Extent	2.86	0.84	High Extent
13.	Family members are more likely to recognize when someone is struggling and respond with empathy and care	2.75	0.83	High Extent	2.93	0.85	High Extent
14.	Open dialogue allows families to work together to solve problems, make decisions, and share responsibilities	2.69	0.82	High Extent	2.95	0.86	High Extent
15.	Regular sharing of feelings, goals, and values deepens mutual understanding and love	2.67	0.82	High Extent	2.87	0.85	High Extent
Grand Total		2.73	0.83		2.90	0.85	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 3 demonstrates the significance of family communication in enhancing overall family well-being among women in Port Harcourt Metropolis. With all mean values meeting or exceeding the

acceptance mean criterion of 2.5 and above, the results indicate that open, respectful and consistent communication fosters emotional safety, mutual understanding and stronger family cohesion. Respondents agreed that when families share feelings, clarify expectations and engage in open dialogue, they build trust, empathy, and cooperation. The table underscores that effective family communication is a critical determinant of healthy relationships and sustained family well-being within the community.

Discussion of Findings

The finding of the study in research question one: To what extent does family communication enhance **emotional resilience** among women in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The study revealed to a High extent that family communication enhances **emotional resilience** among women in Port Harcourt Metropolis. This finding is in collaboration with Gamage (2014), who observed that Strong communication strengthens family bonds and the ability to cope with challenges, including potential conflict. **Emotional resilience** is the ability to **adapt to stress, adversity, or trauma** and bounce back emotionally. One of the strongest foundations for developing emotional resilience especially in children and adolescents is **effective family communication**. When families communicate clearly, supportively, and empathetically, individuals are better equipped to manage emotional challenges and recover from setbacks.

The study in Research Questions 2: How does family communication **reduce anxiety and depression** among Women in Port Harcourt Metropolis indicated that family communication **reduces anxiety and depression** among women in Port Harcourt Metropolis. This study is in the same view with the Burelomova et.al (2018), who noted that Healthy communication can mitigate the psychological impact of family violence, reducing anxiety and depression among family

members. Effective family communication plays a critical role in reducing symptoms of anxiety and depression by creating a safe, supportive, and emotionally validating environment. When family members communicate openly, empathetically, and consistently, individuals especially children, adolescents, and young adults experience greater emotional well-being and resilience.

The findings of the study in Research Question 3: How does family communication enhance **family wellbeing** among Women in Port Harcourt Metropolis showed that family communication enhance **family wellbeing** among Women in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The finding is in the same vein with Deeproze (2014), who noted **effective communication** is one of the **most powerful tools** in promoting and maintaining family wellbeing. It fosters understanding, trust, emotional support, and cooperation among family members, which leads to a more stable and harmonious home environment. **Effective family communication** means clear, honest, respectful, and empathetic exchanges of thoughts, feelings, and needs among family members. **Family wellbeing** encompasses **emotional, psychological, relational, and social wellness** within the family unit.

Conclusion

The findings of this study demonstrate that effective communication plays a critical role in reducing the prevalence of domestic violence among women in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The results clearly show that open, respectful, and empathetic communication between family members fosters understanding, trust, and emotional stability, thereby reducing the likelihood of violent behavior. Families that communicate effectively tend to manage conflict constructively, offer emotional support, and build stronger relationships founded on mutual respect and cooperation. Conversely, households characterized by poor or dysfunctional communication patterns are more likely to experience emotional detachment, misunderstandings, and escalating conflicts that may lead to domestic violence. The study's findings are consistent with existing literature, which indicates that communication serves as a protective mechanism that enhances emotional resilience and prevents the escalation of interpersonal tension into physical or psychological abuse. Previous empirical studies in Nigeria and other parts of Africa have confirmed that communication patterns significantly influence the emotional climate of the family, shaping either peaceful coexistence or conflict escalation. The reviewed literature further emphasizes that when family members are able to express their feelings openly, listen actively, and resolve disagreements amicably, the occurrence of domestic violence is substantially reduced.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher recommends that

1. The government, through Community-Based Women Organizations, should organize capacity-building seminars for women and community leaders to educate and promote effective communication practices and relational harmony within families.

2. Both male and female community leaders should model and promote effective communication to foster resilience in marital relationships.

3. Community leaders should organize seminar programme on how to enhances **family wellbeing**

References

- Adams, A. E., Sullivan, C. M., Bybee, D., & Greeson, M. R. (2012). Development of the scale of economic abuse. *Violence Against Women, 14*(5), 563–588.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1077801208315529>
- Adegoke, T. G., & Oladeji, D. (2016). Communication and domestic violence among married women in Lagos, Nigeria. *Gender & Behaviour, 14*(2), 7287–7297.
- Alzoubi, F. A., & Ali, R. A. (2021). Jordanian Men's and Women's Attitudes Toward Intimate Partner Violence and Its Correlates with Family Functioning and Demographics. *Journal of Interpersonal Violence, 36*(5-6).
- Baller, S. L., & Lewis, K. (2022). Adverse Childhood Experiences, Intimate Partner Violence, and Communication Quality in a College-Aged Sample. *Journal of Family Issues, 43*(9), 420-2437.
- Bandura, A. (1977). *Social learning theory*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall.
- Bandura, A. (1986). Social foundations of thought and action: *A social cognitive theory*. Prentice-Hall.
- Bandura, A. (2001). Social cognitive theory of mass communication. *Media Psychology, 3*(3), 265–299.
- Burelomova, A. S., Gulina, M. A., & Tikhomandritskaya, O. A. (2018). Intimate partner violence: An overview of the existing theories, conceptual frameworks, and definitions. *Psychology in Russia State of the Art, 11*(3), 128–144. <https://doi.org/10.11621/pir.2018.0309>
- Chan, K. L. (2018). Prevalence of dating partner violence and suicidal ideation among male and female university students worldwide. *Journal of Midwifery & Women's Health, 53*(6), 529-537.
- Chukwu, F. A., & Eze, P. N. (2021). Family structure and communication patterns as predictors of spousal abuse in Rivers State, Nigeria. *Journal of Family and Marriage Research, 7*(2), 88–99.
- Chukwu, O., & Eze, N. (2021). Communication dynamics and domestic violence in Rivers State. *Nigerian Journal of Social Studies, 24*(1), 112–128.
- Deeproose, C. (2014). Communication patterns and intimate partner violence: The impact of emotional expression and conflict management. *Journal of Family Communication, 14*(4), 321–336. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15267431.2014.945684>

- Eze, J. E., & Ibekwe, M. E. (2020). Family communication and conflict management among couples in Rivers State. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Management Research*, 6(1), 115–127.
- Fitzpatrick, M. A., & Ritchie, L. D. (1994). Communication schemas in family relationships. *Human Communication Research*, 20(3), 275–301.
- Galvin, K. M., Braithwaite, D. O., & Bylund, C. L. (2018). *Family communication: Cohesion and change* (10th ed.). Routledge.
- Gamage, S. (2014). Domestic violence against women: The role of communication and social support. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 4(1), 150–158.
- Holt, S., Buckley, H., & Whelan, S. (2008). The impact of exposure to domestic violence on children and young people: A review of the literature. *Child Abuse & Neglect*, 32(8), 797–810.
- Ijeoma, K. C., & Ezenwa, M. O. (2019). Women's voices and violence: A qualitative study of domestic abuse in Rivers State. *Journal of Gender Studies in Africa*, 8(1), 44–60.
- Kitzmann, K. M., Gaylord, N. K., Holt, A. R., & Kenny, E. D. (2003). Child witnesses to domestic violence: A meta-analytic review. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology*, 71(2), 339–352. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-006X.71.2.339>
- Kitzmann, K.M. Gaylord, N.K., Holt A.R., & Kenny, E. D. (2003). Child witnesses to domestic violence: A meta-analytic review. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology*, 71(2)339-352.
- Knapp, M. L., & Daly, J. A. (2011). *The Sage handbook of interpersonal communication* (4th ed.). SAGE Publications.
- Koerner, A. F., & Fitzpatrick, M. A. (2002). Toward a theory of family communication. *Communication Theory*, 12(1), 70–91.
- Lawson ,J.(2022).Sociological Theories of Intimate Partner Violence. *Journal of Human Behavior in the Social Environment*, 22(5), 572-590.
- Lloyd, S. A., & Emery, B. C. (2000). The effects of family communication patterns on intimate partner violence. *Journal of Interpersonal Violence*, 15(2), 105–123.
- McLeod, J. M., & Chaffee, S. H. (1972). The construction of social reality. In J. Tedeschi (Ed.), *The social influence processes* (pp. 50–99). Aldine-Atherton.

- Nwankwo, B. O., Obi, T. U., & Nwoke, M. B. (2017). Communication as a predictor of domestic violence in Port Harcourt metropolis. *Nigerian Journal of Communication*, 15(1), 33–49.
- Obasi, T. C., & Igwe, S. N. (2019). Family communication and domestic violence among married couples in Enugu State. *Nigerian Journal of Gender Studies*, 6(1), 42–55.
- Ojedokun, O. A., & Atoi, O. O. (2018). Spousal communication patterns and domestic violence in Nigeria. *Journal of Family Psychology*, 32(3), 402–410.
- Olson, D. (2019). FACES IV and the Circumplex Model: Validation Study. *Journal of Marital and Family Therapy*, 37(1), 64-80.
- Olson, D. H., & Ryder, R. G. (2020). Inventory of Marital Conflicts (IMC): An Experimental Interaction Procedure. *Journal of Marriage and Family*, 32(3), 443-448.
- Onyinye, A., & Alabi, K. (2020). Family interaction and domestic violence among couples in Lagos State. *Journal of Gender Studies*, 19(2), 75–91.
- Onyinye, C. A., & Alabi, T. S. (2020). Gender-based violence and marital communication in Lagos State, Nigeria. *Journal of Gender and Society*, 15(3), 203–218.
- Postmus, J. L., Plummer, S.-B., McMahon, S., Murshid, N. S., & Kim, M. S. (2012). Understanding economic abuse in the lives of survivors. *Journal of Interpersonal Violence*, 27(3), 411–430. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0886260511421669>
- Postmus, J.L. Plummer, S. B., McMahon, S., Murshid, N.S., & Kim, M. S. (2012). Understanding economic abuse in the lives of survivors. *Journal of Interpersonal Violence*, 27 (3), 411-430.
- Santiago, Á. V., Taylor, J. S., Chafey, M. I. J., & Robles, C. Y. I. (2019). Family and intimate partner violence among Puerto Rican university students. *Revista Puertorriqueña de Psicología*, 30(1), 7081.
- Straus, M. A., Gelles, R. J., & Steinmetz, S. K. (1980). *Behind closed doors: Violence in the American family*. Anchor Books..
- Ukonu, M. O., & Eze, C. O. (2021). Influence of family communication patterns on domestic violence against women in South-South Nigeria. *Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 18(2), 76–89.
- Umennuihe C. F. Eze, U.O., & Akpan, E. E. (2023). Family communication patters and marital stability among couples in South East Nigeria. *Journal of Communication and Media Studies*, 15(2), 45-60.
- Umennuihe, C. L., Eya, D. N., Nwobi, C. A., & Obiora, J. I. (2023). Relationship between

family communication patterns and conflict management styles of adolescents in Udenu Local Government Area, Enugu State. *Journal for Family & Society Research*, 2(2), 21–34.

UN Women (2020) The shadow pandemic: Violence against women during COVID-19. UN Women. <https://www.unwomen.org/en/news/in-focus/infocusgender-equality-in-covid-19-response>.

Widom, C. S., & Maxfield, M. G. (2001). An update on the “cycle of violence.” Washington, DC: National Institute of Justice, U.S. Department of Justice. <https://nij.ojp.gov/library/publications/update-cycle-violence>

Wisdom, C. S., & Maxfield, M.G (2001). *An update on the “Cycle of Violence.”* National Institute of Justice Research in Brief. U. S. Department of Justice.

World Health Organization (2021) *Violence Against women prevalence estimates, 2018*. Geneva: World health Organization.

World Health Organization. (2013). Global and regional estimates of violence against women: Prevalence and health effects of intimate partner violence and non-partner sexual violence. World Health Organization. <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789241564625>